

FELLOWSHIP OF THE DATA

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BOOK OF POSTER ABSTRACTS

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List of Posters

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Poster Session 1

Creating an Organisational Data Policy: Process & Reflections

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Broad Topics: Data policy, Data management, Data life cycle, RDM

The responsible handling of research data is vital for fostering scientific progress, disseminating knowledge, and ensuring the traceability of research. The digital transformation of research and society presents new challenges, necessitating central guidelines within research institutions and communities.

To address these challenges, the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (MfN) developed a comprehensive and adaptable catalogue of measures, including recommendations, procedural instructions, and various documentation forms. This catalogue is designed to be maintained and regularly updated to reflect the state of the art. The resulting data policy fills a gap in formal guidance on research and scientific data publication at the MfN.

Developing this policy required input from multiple stakeholders and consideration of all aspects of Research Data Management (RDM), including governance, storage, access, and adherence to FAIR principles. The final policy provides a framework that spans the entire data life cycle, ensuring sustainable and transparent data management.

From this, we share our process, and reflect on key learnings from the policy's development and publication, offering insights that can guide other research institutions and RDM teams in successfully creating and implementing their own data policies.

How OERs succeed with the learning objectives matrix for research data management in university collections

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Broad Topics: Open Educational Resources, Lernzielmatrix zum FDM, Training and Education

SODa strengthens the data literacy and data science skills of all staff involved in university collections. The focus is on OERs for collection-related research data management, providing foundational knowledge, discipline-specific content, current standards, and best practices.

The development of these OERs follows a didactic, methodological, and technical framework. Coherent personas serve as the foundation for targeted learning design, making learners' prior knowledge, needs, motivation, and experience transparent. Research-based learning fosters independence and personal responsibility.

In this context, the learning objectives matrix for RDM is applied and expanded as needed to incorporate additional discipline-specific aspects. The learning objectives set the direction, structure the learning process, and balance knowledge transfer with self-directed learning. They define the use of didactic methods and formats, ensure learning success, and support the practical application of knowledge. Accordingly, problem-based learning approaches are integrated into both synchronous and asynchronous formats and made available as FAIR OERs to the collection and RDM community.

Currently, planned modules include collection development, cataloging, working with data in conservation and restoration documentation, semantic data modeling, data visualization, and image classification.

One Workshop to Rule Them All: Forging RDM skills among PhD Candidates in the Life Sciences

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Broad Topics: Life Science, Student Training, Research Data Management

In June 2023, the Data Stewards at the Faculty of Life Sciences and the Centre for Microbiology and Environmental Systems Science at the University of Vienna launched a new workshop aimed at introducing Ph.D. candidates and Masters students in the life sciences to the fundamentals of research data management (RDM). This course, titled 'Research Data Management for Ph.D. Candidates in the Life Sciences' ^a utilizes a blended learning approach that combines instructional content with various activities to help students practice their skills. Participants complete an online module (approximately 6 hours) before attending two in-person half-day seminars. The online module focuses on information transfer, while the seminars emphasize interactive activities, discussions, and Q&A sessions.

This poster provides a brief overview of the workshop program, along with tips and tricks learned by the Data Stewards. Data from pre- and post-learning assessments are also presented, demonstrating changes in student knowledge levels and comfort with RDM topics. We also discuss our future plans, which include collaboration with UNIVIE doctoral schools, the launch of an Open Science Community, and the adaptation of the course content for students in the Humanities.

^a Feichtinger, M., & Kate, E. J. (2024). feichtingerm/rdmlifesciunivie: Research Data Management for the Life Sciences v1.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10512975>

Come2Data – a national Data Competence Centre with a focus on Saxony

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Broad Topics: Data competence centre, Data literacy, Teaching, Training

Come2Data is one of eleven national data competence centres and is currently under development. It aims to foster awareness and acquisition of data competencies and skills primarily in academia, but also in public administration, industry and the interested public. It follows an interdisciplinary, regional approach by bringing together existing data-related teaching, training and support services of the project partners (TU Chemnitz, TU Dresden, Leipzig University and Saxon State and University Library [SLUB]) as well as expertise, networking and support on research data management (e.g. in SaxFDM), the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) and high-performance computing and analysis methods for data-intensive, interdisciplinary research applications, such as artificial intelligence and data modelling (e.g. in ScaDS.AI).

Information on services and resources will be aggregated and made accessible via a virtual platform serving as a central entry point. Existing teaching offers and materials will be didactically revised, tailored to the learning objectives of different target groups and arranged in learning paths on a modular basis. Findings and solutions developed as part of pilot projects from various disciplines will be integrated. In addition, Come2Data will explore and pilot ways of integrating content related to data literacy into curricula and teaching as well as certification.

What does BERD offer for researchers?

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Broad Topics: Research Data Infrastructure Services, Legal Assistance, Training

BERD@NFDI is the NFDI Consortium for Business, Economic and Related Data. The goal of the Consortium is to empower researchers in the fields of the economic and social sciences with the tools and services needed to harness the full potential of data, while focusing on unstructured data, such as images, videos, audio, and text files. From data collection and indexing to processing, analysing, and preservation, the services of BERD are designed to give support at every step of the entire data lifecycle.

These include among others, Data Portal, Research Data Market Place, Generative AI Directory, OCR Services, and Knowledge Graph Infrastructure.

Our poster will provide a comprehensive overview of these services while giving special attention to the Legal Assistance Service, providing essential tools and guidance for researchers to help them manage legal concerns, and the BERD Academy, which offers courses, workshops and learning materials on data science and data management in relation to core subjects of the Consortium

Data Management Plan template in RSpace: One less tool to simplify research workflow

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Broad Topics: Simplifying research workflows

The effective management of research data begins with creating a data management plan (DMP) for each research project which describes how the research data is handled throughout the research life cycle. However, the importance of proper handling of research data is not realized among researchers as research data management (RDM) is not embedded in their everyday practice. Researchers often get overwhelmed by any additional tools or infrastructure introduced to their research workflows. Therefore, to streamline the research process, we propose a "one less tool" strategy, integrating DMP template into our electronic laboratory notebook (ELN) "RSpace" which helps researchers use existing institutional services and infrastructure instead of adopting an additional platform for creating DMP. This strategy ensures that researchers can focus more on their work while maintaining efficiency in data management. Currently, we are in a trial phase to evaluate the effectiveness of this integration. We assume that researchers are more likely to create their DMPs when the process is integrated in their ELN, reducing the need for an extra effort.

A conceptual framework and actionable steps for communication and engagement in research data management

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Broad Topics: Data manager experience

Research data management (RDM) is increasingly recognized as a key component of good scientific practice within the research workflow due to its role in enhancing research integrity, accessibility, FAIRness and compliance.

To bridge the gap between RDM and stakeholders, particularly researchers, well-planned communication strategies are essential. The purpose of a communication strategy is to address the diverse needs of

stakeholders to create awareness, build trust, address barriers, foster acceptance, encourage engagement and promote action to achieve successful implementation and adoption of RDM. Communication is as essential for the success of RDM as the other action areas, maybe even more important.

Daily tasks of RDM facilitators, such as data managers, data stewards, and data librarians, are overwhelmingly broad, encompassing consulting, competence development and training, policy and standards development, infrastructure and technical services, subject-specific support, and networking and collaboration. Therefore, this poster aims to serve as a guide for RDM facilitators and institutions by highlighting the role of communication in RDM success, observing current State and Challenges in RDM Implementation, identifying stakeholder needs, providing practical recommendations and actionable measures for implementing effective communication strategies, and encouraging sustainable practices by fostering a culture of shared responsibility for data management.

BEXIS2 – a user-friendly Platform for Metadata Management

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Broad Topics: Data management tools, Minimal information standards, Microbiological data

BEXIS2 is a free and open-source community-driven web-based research data management system ^{a, b}. That extensible and customisable system allows the development of new functions and modification of its various components from database schemes to the user interface. In the Microverse cluster, we are instantiating the system as a meta-data management platform, which facilitates the reach metadata annotation using ontologies and controlled vocabularies, data provenance preservation, and semantic integration of different types of data acquired in microbiological experiments or collected in the natural environment. In this contribution, we will provide technical details on the BEXIS2 architecture, demonstrate current development, and discuss several cases of minimal information standards (REMBI ^c, MARGARITAS ^d, MIAPE-GE ^e) implementation.

The work is supported by the grant provided by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation), Projekt 'EXC 2051: Balance of the Microverse', No 390713860.

^a Chamanara *et al.* (2021) BEXIS2: A FAIR-aligned data management system for biodiversity, ecology and environmental data. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 9: e72901. DOI: [10.3897/BDJ.9.e72901](https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.9.e72901)

^b BEXIS2 GitHub repository: <https://github.com/BEXIS2>

^c Sarkans *et al* (2021) REMBI: Recommended Metadata for Biological Images—enabling reuse of microscopy data in biology. *Nat Methods* 18, 1418–1422 DOI:[10.1038/s41592-021-01166-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01166-8)

^d MARGARITAS: MICHl Standard for Reporting Liquid-State NMR Experiments of Small Molecules. <https://fairsharing.org/5897>.

^e Gibson *et al* (2008) Guidelines for reporting the use of gel electrophoresis in proteomics. *Nat Biotechnol.* 26(8):863-4. DOI: [10.1038/nbt0808-863](https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt0808-863).

TUM Research Data Hub - Services and Challenges

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Broad Topics: Research data projects, Physical research data

The poster presents the way in which the new Research Data Hub organizes its central infrastructure as a collaborative project between the University Library and the Munich Data Science Institute. It shows different training formats and counseling services for research projects and the specific challenges that arise with the needs of heterogeneous projects at TUM.

The poster shows the development of the different services from the first days of research data management at the University Library to the inception of the Hub in 2023 and to the present date. It illustrates how the use of the services has changed over time and how these changes have served to refine the service portfolio of the Hub. The section ends with an outlook on future developments.

In addition, the poster presents one exemplary challenge in the counseling context that gave an impulse to extend the service portfolio of the Hub. The Institute of Machine Tools and Industrial Management contacted the Research Data Hub in order to standardize the management of physical data. The poster shows how this challenge led to the development of a checklist that could be reused in other cases and gave the impulse for the development of new services.

RDM, FAIR, and data sharing practices and perceptions of people who work with sensitive health data

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Broad Topics: RDM, FAIR, health data, sensitive data

Transforming how sensitive health data is managed and shared is an urgent challenge. However, proper adoption of RDM and FAIR practices is blocked by technical and cultural barriers, which need to be investigated and understood to drive widespread culture change.

To explore the barriers to adopting good RDM and FAIR practices in health data and discover health researchers' current practices, knowledge, and understanding of RDM/FAIR, we interviewed researchers in the Centre for Musculoskeletal Research at the University of Manchester.

Nine researchers were interviewed; most had not heard of FAIR. All agreed that RDM and FAIR are important and that motivations outweighed the barriers. Motivations included producing trustworthy, high

quality science, maximising data use, and future proofing research. Limitations included limitations in time/resources, knowledge, infrastructure and human support. Unique to sensitive health data is the volume of legal and ethical "red tape", and the resources needed to navigate this. Four researchers mentioned dropping research ideas and collaborations because of this.

Further research is needed into the cultural barriers to good RDM/FAIR practices among sensitive health data researchers, particularly to investigate whether this is unique to researchers at UoM, and how to overcome barriers and create widespread shifts in practices.

Strategies for implementing research data management at ISAS using openBIS

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Broad Topics: Research Data Management, ELN - LIMS

Effective research data management (RDM) is crucial for ensuring data integrity, reproducibility, and compliance with institutional policies. OpenBIS, an open-source RDM platform, offers comprehensive solutions for electronic lab notebooks, inventory management, and sample tracking. However, its high flexibility necessitates tailored configurations and user training.

We conducted a pilot project at a proteomics laboratory in collaboration with the University of Magdeburg to evaluate OpenBIS for metaproteomics research. This project focuses on assessing OpenBIS's data structure, automation capabilities, and suitability for streamlining workflows. Additionally, we are developing training materials to support user onboarding and facilitate adoption at ISAS. A key objective is to enhance researcher engagement by integrating automation and enabling cross-data studies for scalable and efficient data management.

Insights from this pilot will guide best practices for broader implementation at ISAS, ensuring standardized data management, improved collaboration, and compliance with research policies. By involving multiple research groups, we aim to foster interdisciplinary cooperation and uphold high-quality RDM standards.

Data Manager: A data management solution for the life sciences

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Broad Topics: Data Manager application

Effective research data management is fundamental to ensure the integrity and reproducibility of scientific research. We present the Tübingen Data Manager application, a FOSS that not only stores data of the plethora of omics technologies alongside its associated metadata, but also enables sharing and re-use of the data towards a FAIR and Open Data future.

The Data Manager application was developed at **QBiC**, one of the main core facilities on the University of Tübingen, in close collaboration with domain experts (life science) and research software engineers to support users throughout the research data lifecycle. It provides an integrated environment that spans from the Data Management Plan to the publication of research outputs, capturing general project meta-data, experimental design, raw data acquisition, and downstream analysis.

The Data Manager provides researchers with flexible data-sharing capabilities while ensuring guidance through step-by-step documentation at every stage of the data lifecycle. To enhance data provenance tracking and interoperability, the application integrates ORCID and ROR, as well as many ontologies via the TIB terminology service. By integrating comprehensive scientific project management functionalities, our solution not only facilitates the reproducibility of analysis but also ensures the transparency and reusability of the applied analytical workflows and research outcomes.

Data Steward Network Lower Saxony: Development, competence building and networking measures

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Broad Topics: Research data management, Data steward, Lower Saxony, Networking, Collaboration

We present the Data Steward Network Lower Saxony, which was created through the initiatives of the **Joint Lab Future Libraries & Research Data** and the **FDM-ndsHAW** project and embedded within the state initiative RDM Lower Saxony (**FDM NDS**).

On the basis of definitions of the role data steward (Seidlmayer et al., 2023^a), we discuss the characteristics of the data stewards in Lower Saxony and highlight the development of the network. The Data Steward regulars' table will take centre stage as a platform for networking and professional exchange. We also present support services such as onboarding measures, skills development, and other networking opportunities through Pillar 1 and Pillar 2 of the state initiative.

Finally, we will reflect on our experiences to date and provide an outlook on the further development of the network. The poster and our insights might be of interest for data stewards and anyone interested in community and network building.

^a Seidlmayer, E., Hoffmann, F., Dierkes, J., Lindstädt, B., Depping, R., & Förstner, K. U. (2023). *Forschung unterstützen: Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen*. PUBLISSO. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006441397>

Spreading Research Data Management at Universities of Applied Sciences: Challenges & Strategies

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Broad Topics: RDM at Universities of Applied Science

RDM is essential for ensuring data security, long-term usability, and compliance with institutional and funding requirements. This project FORTH-BW develops a practical, secure, and researcher-friendly RDM system tailored to Universities of Applied Sciences (UAS) in Baden-Württemberg. A central outcome is the FORTH-BW network, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange across universities.

Dissemination plays a crucial role in integrating RDM into UAS environments, characterized by applied research, shorter project cycles, and industry collaborations. Strategies include workshops, train-the-trainer programs, online courses, to equip researchers, students, and institutional staff with practical RDM skills.

Key challenges include data loss, lack of documentation, and unclear ownership, addressed through institutional RDM policies, persistent storage solutions, and embedding RDM in funding applications. By promoting collaboration, transparency, and sustainable archiving, the project ensures that RDM becomes an integral part of applied research at UAS.

VirJenDB: the metadata-centric Virus database from FSU Jena

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Broad Topics: Virus Research Infrastructure, Metadata, FAIR data, Research Data Lifecycle

Viral databases are vital for bioinformatics-driven virological research; however, research is hindered by errors in user-submitted sequences and metadata. Despite ongoing community efforts to curate virus metadata and establish standards, structured models for specific virus groups are needed to enhance FAIR data across disciplines like ecology, medicine, and agriculture. The VirJenDB virus sequence database presents a metadata-driven approach to support virus researchers at multiple steps of the research data lifecycle. An extensive metadata catalogue was harvested along with virus sequences from publicly available sources, including databases such as NCBI Virus, ENA and the BVBR, and community-driven standards like the MIGS-VI and ENV-O. The VJDB team leverages this dataset in the development of web-accessible services, including customizable metadata templates which integrate with our pilot ENA submission wizard and can be populated using existing ontologies and database suggestions to guide researchers and encourage the deposition of metadata-rich virus sequences to the ENA. In summary, VJDB aims to empower researchers with a web portal to support virus research from the initial stages to publication and beyond. Thus, the VJDB will help develop extensive virus metadata standards from and for sharing with the research community.

LiveDocs: Crafting Interactive Development Environments From Research Findings

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Broad Topics: Research Dissemination, Open Research

The “Collaborative Research Center 1456 - Mathematics of Experiment” (CRC 1456) aims at the development of mathematical theory and tools to extract maximal information from data acquired in experimental research in natural sciences. This project is aligned with Open Science ideals, which puts its infrastructure subproject (INF) under the mission of promoting such principles throughout other subprojects. The INF project works primarily under three fronts: research data management (RDM) support, research dissemination, and training on RDM-relevant topics.

Such effort yielded fruitful outcomes such as the development of a platform for research dissemination: **LiveDocs**. LiveDocs is an initiative of the CRC 1456 on tackling common issues of reproducibility and re-usability in scientific publications. LiveDocs is proposed as a concept alongside a collection of methods that enable scientists to provide research findings under an interactive development environment, allowing users from a broader audience to easily reproduce research findings by re-running scripts pertaining to a publication under such environment. This approach lowers the barriers to access and

comprehend research methods and findings, which facilitates scientific exchange and fosters knowledge advancement.

In this poster, readers will be presented with an in-depth visualization on LiveDocs and some LiveDocs showcases.

Data Stewards, the Architects of FAIR

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Broad Topics: Challenges of Data Stewardship

Data stewards play a critical role in implementing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices, yet their position remains undefined, under-supported, and undervalued. Despite being responsible for bridging researchers, IT teams, librarians, and policymakers, data stewards often find themselves stuck in the middle: expected to guide FAIR implementation but lacking the authority to enforce policies.

One major challenge is the blurry job description – data stewardship varies widely between institutions, with no standardized role definition, career path, or training framework. Stewards are expected to be experts in metadata, IT, open science, and research workflows, while also serving as educators and policy advisors – often without formal training in these areas. Their work is further complicated by institutional barriers, including a lack of policies supporting their role and insecure funding structures that limit long-term impact.

Without clear mandates or authority, data stewards rely on voluntary compliance from researchers, making FAIR adoption inconsistent. To address these challenges, institutions must standardize training, establish clear job roles, and empower data stewards with decision-making influence. Recognizing data stewardship as a permanent and essential profession is key to ensuring that FAIR principles move beyond theory into sustainable practice.

A Large-scale FAIR Research Data Infrastructure for Environmental Time Series Data

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Broad Topics: Transformative shift, Self-organized RDM, User self-service, Large-scale infrastructure, STA

In Environmental Sciences, Time-series data is key to, for example, monitoring environmental processes and validating Earth system models. A major issue is the lack of a consistent data availability standard aligned with the FAIR principles, but the Helmholtz Earth and Environment DataHub is working with the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration project STAMPLATE to address this.

The seven participating research centers are building a large-scale infrastructure using the Open Geospatial Consortium's SensorThings API (STA) as the central data interface. It is linked to other community-driven tools, such as sensor and device management systems, data ingestion systems, and the Earth Data Portal (www.earth-data.de) with highly customizable viewers.

Our custom, semantic metadata profile augments STA's core data model with domain-specific information. This ensures that metadata entered in any user self-service is also displayed in the Earth Data Portal along with the ingested data.

The operationalization of the framework and its subsequent integration into research data workflows is imminent, thereby rendering long-term, nationwide measurements spanning decades available. Concurrently, our RDM processes are undergoing a transformative shift, moving from manual, person-based to self-organized, digital-supported workflows.

This poster presents the fundamental elements of our initiative and the associated challenges. It also encourages new domains to get involved.

Poster Session 2

Collaborative processing and reuse of the Research Data Scarytales as an open educational resource

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Broad Topics: Open Educational Ressources - Reuse of Research Data Scary Tales

In 2020, the TKFDM developed our "Research Data Scarytales" based on the well-known card game "Black Stories". Each Research Data Scarytale describes a scenario in which something goes wrong with research data. The aim of the game is to guess what exactly happened based on a teaser and a picture.

In order to future-proof this popular format and open it up to the FDM community, the TKFDM has made it available for reuse from the outset. The broad application in practice and the associated experience resulted in a series of comments on how to expand the material that could be incorporated iteratively. For example, numbering was added to the cards and keywords were assigned. This enables a topic-adapted selection for use in teaching and training.

In addition, we are planning a transition from editing the stories within TKFDM to collaborative additions by the FDM community as a whole. To this end, images and texts from the Research Data Scarytales have been transferred to a GitLab repository.

The TKFDM is planning a series of workshops around the Scarytales and the collaboration possibilities to actively promote community building and practice the Git functionalities.

Data Stewardship and Coscine

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DOI: [10.11588/heidok.00036358](https://doi.org/10.11588/heidok.00036358)

Broad Topics: Coscine, FAIR principles, Automation

Coscine is RWTH's solution for safely and FAIRly storing and archiving research data and metadata. By requiring metadata, Coscine ensures data meets FAIR principles, making it reusable within the scientific community. Users create projects containing resources that house data linked with metadata profiles. If publicly available, metadata can be searched. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) enhance findability.

This poster illustrates how data stewards at RWTH support researchers in using Coscine. We highlight three key areas: creating tailored metadata profiles, automating data workflows, and connecting services like ELNs.

Coscine offers fillable forms for recording metadata, allowing researchers to establish custom metadata profiles while promoting standardization. Data stewards assist in selecting and structuring metadata and creating profiles, such as for Preclinical Imaging or Flow Cytometry.

Once profiles are set, data storage is integrated into Coscine projects. To streamline workflows, data stewards develop Python scripts using the Coscine SDK, extracting metadata from research files and linking it with stored data.

Researchers also use other tools, including ELNs. REST APIs enable automated metadata transfer into Coscine, bridging ELN limitations. A native integration is in development to simplify these workflows, with potential for broader application.

Certificate of Advanced Studies Forschungsdatenmanagement (CAS FDM) – The bwFDM training program for Data Stewards and RDM personnel

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Broad Topics: RDM training, Certificate, Microcredentials, Data stewards

The Federal State Initiative for Research Data Management in Baden-Württemberg (bwFDM) has developed a ten-month certificate course for Data Stewards and other data professionals, starting in October 2025. A distinctive feature of this course is that participants will receive a Certificate of Advanced Studies (CAS) as well as microcredentials for specific learning units. The CAS FDM encompasses all key areas of RDM and equips participants with relevant soft skills, including communication techniques, teaching skills, project management, and change management. The curriculum consists of six learning units: (1) Basic Concepts, (2) Data Organization, (3) Law and Ethics, (4) Technical Infrastructure, (5) Consulting, Training, and Project Management, and (6) Data Manipulation and Versioning. During the final phase of the course, participants undertake a mandatory project related to the curriculum to qualify for the CAS. Microcredentials are available for learning units (1) Basic Concepts, (3) Law and Ethics, and (4) Technical Infrastructure. The course is structured to be manageable alongside work: The workload is approximately eight hours per week, which includes three hours of interactive online training. A significant portion of the training consists of self-learning units. The course is conducted in German. Registration will open soon.

Navigating the challenges of data management in the DAM research missions

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Broad Topics: Data management working group, Large-scale projects, Experiences, Lessons learned

The research missions of the German Marine Research Alliance (DAM) focus on highly relevant topics for society and support science-based decisions for the sustainable use and management of coastal areas and oceans. In these large-scale, transdisciplinary and cross-institutional projects, effective data management is an important prerequisite to ensure the long-term preservation and reusability of research data. Our working group supports scientists involved in the DAM research missions to make their research data FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. We regularly discuss various challenges in research data management such as reservation towards data sharing, or a lack of knowledge, personnel and resources to implement sustainable data management. Consequently, we develop and offer solutions, formulate recommendations and organize informational and training events. We highlight the advantages of FAIR data handling, promote the connection to DAM-related activities such as the project "Underway" Research Data and the Marine Data Portal, and support data publishing and archiving e.g. in PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science. We found that existing and dedicated data managers, good communication and training, as well as practical technical solutions are key to supporting scientists to manage their data FAIRly.

NFDI4Microbiota Helpdesk

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Broad Topics: Support, Data Stewards, Helpdesk

NFDI4Microbiota (the German National Research Data Infrastructure for Microbiota Research) is dedicated to supporting microbiologists with data access, analysis services, data and metadata standards, and training. The consortium's **Helpdesk** serves as a single point of contact for the German microbiology research community for all questions related to microbial (omics) data and associated metadata. We welcome questions from anyone - students, researchers, data stewards and others - working with microbial data, regardless of organism (bacteria, archaea, eukaryotic microorganisms, viruses), environment (soil, plants, host-associated and water) or data type (e.g. nucleic acid sequences, functional genomics, image data, proteins).

Here we present the Helpdesk workflow for connecting microbiologists with NFDI4Microbiota experts, as well as some of the most frequently asked questions (FAQs) and their answers. By streamlining access to support and key information resources, NFDI4Microbiota enables microbiologists to make their research more efficient, reproducible and collaborative.

From Data to Credits: Using ReadMe, Markdown, and Dublin Core for Better Documentation

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15127380](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15127380)

Broad Topics: RDM Fundamentals

Effective documentation is crucial for good research data management (RDM) enabling reproducibility, data sharing, and collaboration. A common standard for information sharing in data publication is to write text files as generic "ReadMe"s. Using the markup language Markdown and the Dublin Core vocabulary allows for formatted and structured documentation. The enrichment of datasets with these metadata, including licenses such as Creative Commons, ensures findability, attribution, and reusability in open science publication, as well as easy-to-understand descriptions for research partners. Furthermore, utilizing parsers to extract and validate metadata can streamline the documentation process. I will provide some practical tips and examples ^a for implementing these concepts establishing a robust data life cycle in your research and facilitating data sharing and collaboration.

^a Dockhorn, R. (2025). From Data to Credits: Using ReadMe, Markdown, and Dublin Core for Better Documentation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14848834>

Enhancing Research Data Management: A Chemistry-Specific Exercise Catalogue

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Broad Topics: Training material

Workshops for researchers or students on research data management (RDM) are often offered by central RDM service facilities. Although the basic aspects of RDM are discussed, there are often no discipline-specific examples or tools, so participants often lack a tangible relevance to their own research activities.

NFDI4Chem has been offering RDM training courses since 2022, teaching the basics of RDM in a chemistry context. To enable the reusability of the workshop, NFDI4Chem has developed an exercise catalogue ^a that provides RDM staff with specific examples for designing a workshop with a high degree of practical relevance to chemistry. The catalogue categorises exercises by RDM topic and exercise type. Information on exercise duration, a detailed description with equipment requirements and examples enable direct implementation in RDM trainings.

The exercises use portals such as the PubChem database, the Chemotion and RADAR4Chem repositories or the NFDI4Chem terminology service. The importance of metadata can be explored using reaction schemes, NMR spectra or microscopy images. A catalogue of requirements for the use of ELNs or a DMP based on a chemical project description can be developed. Suggestions for generic exercises with chemistry-specific recommendations, e.g. on data lifecycle, FAIR principles or process management complete the exercise catalogue.

^a Hausen, D. A., Schröter, A., Andres, A.-C., & Golub-Overbeck, B. (2024, August 21). 27 FAIR RDM exercises - A (Chemistry-specific) Catalogue. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13353021>

Institutional Set-up of a Research Data Service for Tropical Marine Research

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Broad Topics: Infrastructure

In 2020, the Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research (ZMT) established the Research Data Service (RDS) working group to support the management of research data in its scientific projects. The RDS provides a secure technical infrastructure for cross-border collaboration and expert advice to scientists at ZMT and its (inter)national partners.

This poster shows how frameworks for support have evolved until today and where they are heading in the future. The RDS provides guidance throughout the entire data lifecycle – from project planning to completion and data reuse. Researchers collaborate in the ZMT DataCloud and the computing cluster ZMT DataLab. Additionally, the ZMT DataPortal provides access to historical and current (meta)data from ZMT research data.

The success of the RDS at ZMT is based on the interdisciplinary expertise of its team. Specialists in data management for the natural and social sciences, (geospatial) data collection, research systems engineering, and databases work closely together to develop tailored solutions. At a strategic level, management decisions shape the direction, priorities, and integration of the service within ZMT, as well as its multi-scale research landscape. This makes ZMT a compelling example of institutional research data management, combining expert-led operational assistance with a strong strategic foundation.

USS Data Steward: Manual for new crew members

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Broad Topics: RDM Newbie Jumpstart, Humanities, Tips & Tricks

Your deployment on the USS Data Steward is now in force. This is your first day - welcome to the crew! To enable a smooth onboarding, your more experienced colleagues have prepared this manual with eight recommendations for your first months on the job.

When making the career switch to a data steward*ess (be it from research or from another position in the library/RDM environment), you might wonder where to start and what to consider. This poster offers recommendations based on three years experience as a data stewardess serving a large humanities faculty at a large university (and a much longer experience as a Trekkie).

How to organize my data? Folder structuring for a clean digital workplace

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15165959](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15165959)

Broad Topics: Folder/filing structure, File naming, Versioning, Training, Experience RDM, NFDI4Biodiversity

Effective data management is crucial for capturing and reusing research data, and a well-organized storage structure is essential for achieving this goal. Without a clear folder structure and a transparent filing system, data often becomes untraceable and difficult or impossible to locate. The poster addresses the role of good scientific practice and the FAIR criteria (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) in maintaining a well-organized digital workspace. Common problems that arise from poor data management will be discussed, along with strategies for avoiding them. The poster aims to provide a starting point for tidying up your digital workspace, and is relevant to researchers at all institutions, including the FBN in Dummerstorf, where they need to handle large amounts of data in their daily work.

Base4NFDI: Supporting Basic Services Through And For NFDI

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Broad Topics: Basic Services, Base4NFDI, NFDI

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) is developing cross-disciplinary basic services to support FAIR research data management (RDM). These services address common needs across NFDI consortia, such as federated identity management (IAM4NFDI), persistent identifiers (PID4NFDI), and RDM Trainings (RDMT4NFDI). The **Base4NFDI** initiative provides funding and a framework to establish and sustain these services.

Basic services integrate existing solutions and ensure interoperability at national and international levels. Their development follows a requirement-driven approach, involving research software engineers (RSE) who adapt services to consortia needs, incorporate FAIR principles, and promote open science. Sustainable operation requires long-term financial and organizational planning.

Service Stewards play a key role in this process by acting as intermediaries between technical teams and user communities. They facilitate communication, gather requirements, and ensure usability, making basic services more effective and widely adopted. Their coordination efforts help align services with FAIR principles and broader RDM goals while also addressing legal and privacy issues to ensure compliance and responsible data stewardship.

This poster explores how NFDI's basic services, supported by RSEs and Service Stewards, enhance FAIR data management and sustainable research infrastructure. Join us to discuss strategies for advancing cross-disciplinary service development in NFDI and beyond.

Strategies for Effective RDM Training in Chemistry

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Broad Topics: Training concepts

In an era where the integrity and accessibility of research data are increasingly important, sound data management skills among chemists are essential. NFDI4Chem, the chemistry consortium in the NFDI, is addressing this need by leading a series of strategic training programmes aimed at enhancing research data management (RDM) competencies across the chemical community.

One pillar of these strategies is the utilization of best practice examples to teach data literacy competencies throughout the curriculum. This approach ensures that students not only become proficient in their scientific expertise but also develop skills in managing chemical data effectively. On the researcher's level, NFDI4Chem offers workshops tailored to their needs, providing them with chemistry-specific recommendations in organising, sharing, and preserving data. Another cornerstone of our training program is the courses on Chemotion ELN, an electronic laboratory notebook specifically designed for chemists.

Additionally, we provide a comprehensive suite of training materials, accessible to both educators and researchers, to support continuous learning and adaptation in research data practices.

Through these multifaceted training activities, NFDI4Chem is setting a new standard for data management within the chemical sciences, fostering a culture of efficiency, transparency, and provision of FAIR data.

How to improve data curation in the Biodiversity Exploratories and BEXIS2

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Broad Topics: Tools, Support, Curation

The poster focuses on a review and outline of options for improving the data management workflow in the **Biodiversity Exploratories** and **BEXIS2** data management software.

The Biodiversity Exploratories (BE) project is a German research platform. Scientists from different research institutions are investigating biodiversity in grasslands and forests. Since 2006, projects have collected a wide range of data (e.g., tabular data, R-scripts, images, GIS data). To promote data management, good data quality and to encourage data sharing between projects over time, a data management team was always part of the BE and the data management software of the BE (BEXIS) was launched in 2007.

In the following years, the data curation workflow, data policy, and software features were revised several times to meet the growing demands on data quality and to meet the FAIR principles. In 2021, we migrated to BEXIS2 data management software.

Last year, we developed an application that automatically creates standardized GitHub issues for each newly created dataset to document data curation, and sends curation emails. The next step for the BE data management team and the BEXIS2 team is to integrate data curation into the BEXIS2 data management software to automate and reduce the workload of curation.

We want to do better, so do you? – Let's share our experiences on RDM workshops!

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Broad Topics: RDM, Workshops

What does it take to conduct a successful training event? What are the most relevant experiences (for us) in aspects such as useful Zoom tools, necessary documents for good functioning, and previous management to facilitate the organisation?

In the last year and a half, we have run several online and face-to-face courses within the FAIRagro project and we want to share with the community the improvements we have observed in the way of conducting our courses, the advantages of some of the tools we have used and the drawbacks we have had to face. But we don't want to just present our own experiences but to create an interactive poster in which everyone can share what advantages, disadvantages and novelties they find useful or completely useless. We also want to include in the debate other tools to use that we don't know about so that we can all improve for future events.

The Role of the Generic Data Steward in Connecting Research and Research Data Management: Initial Insights from the CARDS Project

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Broad Topics: Generic Data Stewardship

The **CARDS project** (Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support) aims to integrate research data management (RDM) into everyday research practices in a needs-based and sustainable manner. As part of this initiative, the generic Data Steward model is being evaluated within the Excellence Clusters of the Berlin University Alliance (BUA). The primary objectives of this subproject are to enhance data management practices, while at the same time pilot such a data stewardship arrangement and assess its efficacy.

In this model, the Data Steward collaborates with research teams, providing specialized assistance with specific RDM tasks such as data structuring, storage, cleaning, documentation, and publication. Current activities include adapting data management scripts, developing standard operating procedures (SOPs) for research data handling, analyzing existing workflows, raising awareness of relevant regulations and communicating with IT at the various institutions.

This poster introduces the concept of the generic Data Steward model, shares key lessons learned from its implementation, and explores strategies for further strengthening its impact.

Research Data Management in de.NBI/ELIXIR DE

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DOI: [10.7490/f1000research.1120218.1](https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1120218.1) (similar poster)

Broad Topics: RDM, FAIR, Community, Network, Life Science

Life science research is generating large amounts of data aiming to solve complex biological questions. To support researchers in handling these data challenges, the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI) and its corresponding ELIXIR Node (ELIXIR-DE) provide free-of-charge tools, services, training, and compute resources. Their efforts focus on enabling big data-driven research through easy-to-use bioinformatics tools, corresponding training activities, and the offering of compute resources via the de.NBI Cloud.

When handling big data related analysis, Research Data Management (RDM) has emerged as a key topic in the Life Sciences in Europe. Generated data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reproducible (FAIR) within the Life Science research community. To ensure that this data is FAIR, it is essential to create effective structures for data sharing and usage. This involves reaching a consensus on data standards and fostering both knowledge and expertise in the field.

de.NBI/ELIXIR-DE is supporting these processes by providing access to RDM resources and training at both the national and European levels. Further, exchanging best practices and expertise is part of the de.NBI/ELIXIR-DE network and the broader ELIXIR Communities. The ELIXIR RDM Community is one of the examples where RDM activities in ELIXIR have been strengthened.